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Measuring what matters: tracking climate adaptation processes and outcomes for smallholder producers in the agriculture sector

Deliverable 4: First Draft Systematic Map (Preliminary)

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Systematic Map Protocol

Note: This document is a preliminary first draft of the systematic map, based primarily on Scopus database records and illustrative extracted data. Multi-database integration (Web of Science, CAB Abstracts, AGRIS, Academic Search Premier) and grey literature searching are ongoing. All figures and counts will be updated in Deliverable 5.

Keywords: Climate Adaptation, Adaptation Outcomes, Adaptation Process, Smallholder Farmers, Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E), Agriculture

1. Executive Summary

This document presents the first draft of the systematic map of methods used to track and measure climate adaptation processes and outcomes for smallholder producers in the agriculture sector in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The map is preliminary, based on Scopus database records, and clearly labelled as such. Final results integrating all planned databases and full human data extraction will be delivered in Deliverable 5.

A total of 39,113 records were identified across five databases. After applying the PCCM eligibility criteria at the title and abstract stage, 8,555 records were retained for full-text review. Full-text retrieval is complete: 3,476 full texts were retrieved across all databases. LLM-assisted data extraction has produced a coded dataset of 2,750 studies, which form the basis of the evidence gap map and searchable database presented here.

A parallel multi-database search (Web of Science, CAB Abstracts, AGRIS, Academic Search Premier) identified 8,187 additional records, of which 2,337 were included at the abstract screening stage. Full-text retrieval and LLM-assisted data extraction for these databases are now complete and integrated into the results presented here.

2. Background

The background, theory of change, stakeholder engagement process, and full PCCM eligibility criteria underpinning this systematic map are documented in Deliverable 3 (Final Systematic Map Protocol, January 2026). This section provides a brief overview for context.

A growing number of climate adaptation interventions are being deployed across the agriculture sector to support smallholder producers in LMICs. Despite growing investment, a central challenge persists: how to measure the effectiveness of these interventions. Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) in this space is particularly complex, due to long timeframes, evolving climate baselines, terminological differences, and attribution challenges. This systematic map responds to these challenges by systematically identifying, characterising, and comparing the methods used to assess climate adaptation interventions in the agriculture sector, with a focus on smallholder producers in LMICs.

3. Methods

This systematic map follows the protocol published as Deliverable 3 (Bristlepine Resilience Consultants, January 2026). A brief summary is provided here; readers are referred to that document for full methodological details.

3.1 Search Strategy

Searches were conducted in Scopus (Elsevier) in January 2026, using a structured Boolean search string developed around the PCCM framework (Population: smallholder producers; Concept: adaptation processes and outcomes; Context: climate hazards, LMICs, agriculture sector; Methodological Focus: measurement, indicators, monitoring and evaluation approaches).

Searches were restricted to literature published from 2005 onward and to English, French, and Spanish language sources. A total of 17,021 records were retrieved.

Additional databases searched in parallel include Web of Science Core Collection, CAB Abstracts, AGRIS, and Academic Search Premier. Abstract screening, full-text retrieval, and LLM-assisted data extraction for these databases are now complete and integrated into the results presented here. Grey literature sources (approximately 20 repositories per \$3.3 of the protocol) are also being searched.

3.2 Deduplication

Records from all databases were deduplicated using a multi-stage matching algorithm: exact DOI match, then exact title and year match, then fuzzy title similarity (Jaccard ≥ 0.85). Scopus records were used as the primary reference set; net-new records from other databases were identified against this base.

3.3 Screening

Title and abstract screening was conducted using a validated LLM-assisted screening tool (Ollama/Llama3), calibrated against the PCCM eligibility criteria. Two calibration rounds were completed prior to full-corpus screening, achieving a sensitivity of 0.966–0.970 against human-coded benchmarks. All 17,021 Scopus records were screened at the title and abstract stage. Records with missing abstracts (1,328 records, 7.8%) were flagged for manual review.

3.4 Random Selection and Data Extraction

Given the large volume of included studies, full manual data extraction across the entire corpus is not feasible within the scope of this review. A random subset of included studies was therefore selected for human full-text screening and data extraction and analysis. The subset was drawn using a reproducible random sampling procedure from the pool of included title-abstract records.

The size of the sampled subset was determined using a convergence-based approach. Human coders first screen the full-text using the protocol eligibility criteria. As applicable, a reason for exclusion is noted. Included studies, estimated at 80% based on a sample previously assessed, moved on to data extraction.

Data extraction proceeded iteratively in batches, with ongoing tracking of newly identified adaptation focus categories, methodological approaches, and coding refinements. Convergence was considered to be reached when successive batches yielded minimal new information, defined as fewer than 5% new codes or substantive refinements across two consecutive batches. An initial random sample of 100 studies will be drawn, with additional batches incorporated in increments of 100 studies as needed until convergence is achieved. This approach ensures that the sample size is sufficient to robustly characterize the diversity of adaptation measurement approaches while avoiding unnecessary extraction of redundant information.

Data are extracted using a structured codebook comprising 16 fields, including publication year, country/region, producer type, climate hazard type, adaptation intervention type, methodological

approach, outcome type, and marginalization dimensions. The sampled subset will form the basis for the evidence gap map, descriptive statistics, and methodological synthesis presented in Deliverable 5. The full set of included studies is retained in the searchable database to ensure transparency and to support future analysis.

4. Preliminary Results

4.1 Search and Screening Summary

A total of 39,113 records were retrieved across five databases (Table 2). After deduplication, 25,208 unique records remained. Title and abstract screening identified 8,555 records for inclusion, of which 3,476 full texts were retrieved. Full-text screening and data extraction are complete across all databases (2,750 included for coding). Figure 1 presents the ROSES flow diagram for the search and screening process. Table 1 presents search and screening results across all databases.

Table 1. Search and screening results by database. WoS = Web of Science; CAB = CAB Abstracts; ASP = Academic Search Premier. *Full-text screening and data extraction complete for Scopus; remaining databases to be completed prior to Deliverable 5.

Database	Records Returned	After Dedup	Abstract Screening Included	Full Texts Retrieved	Full Texts Screened (all databases)	Included for Coding (all databases)
Scopus	17,021	17,021	6,218	2,644	—	—
Web of Science	15,179	4,683	1,137	552		
CAB Abstracts	5,723	3,229	1,133	260		
Acad. Search Premier	1,187	274	66	20		
AGRIS	3	1	1	0		
Total	39,113	25,208	8,555	3,476	3,423	2,750

ROSES Flow Diagram — Scopus + WoS + CAB + ASP + AGRIS
 Record flow across all screening stages · hover nodes and links for detail · other-database full-text retrieval pending

Figure 1 presents the ROSES (Reporting Standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses) flow diagram for the Scopus search and screening process

4.2 Evidence Gap Map

Figure 2 presents the preliminary evidence gap map, showing the distribution of 2,646 coded studies across key dimensions: geography, producer type, adaptation intervention domain, measurement methodology, and temporal coverage. The map is interactive and available at the searchable database link below.

Key preliminary observations (to be confirmed and expanded in Deliverable 5):

- Geographic distribution: Studies are concentrated in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, with sparser coverage of East Asia, Latin America, and the Middle East and North Africa.

Figure 3. Geographic distribution of coded studies (all databases, preliminary).

Figure 4. Regional distribution of coded studies by country (all databases, preliminary).

- Producer types: Crop producers dominate the evidence base; pastoralists, fishers, and forestry producers are underrepresented.
- Methodological focus: Survey-based and quasi-experimental approaches are most common. Participatory and mixed-methods approaches represent a smaller but growing share of the evidence.

Figure 5. Distribution of methodological approaches across coded studies (all databases, preliminary).

- Temporal trends: Publication volume has grown substantially since 2010, with notable acceleration post-2015 (Paris Agreement).

Figure 6. Temporal trends in publication volume, 1990–2024 (all databases, preliminary).

5. Searchable Database

The preliminary searchable database is available at:

<https://main.d3a9jahzuu7xai.amplifyapp.com/systematic-map>

The database includes all 2,750 records coded in the preliminary, exploratory data extraction pass. Users can filter by country, producer type, adaptation domain, methodology, and publication year. A CSV download of the full dataset is available on the same page.

Note: the database will be updated continuously as multi-database integration, random selection and human full-text screening and data extraction are completed. The final version will be published with Deliverable 5.

6. Limitations

This preliminary report has several limitations that will be addressed in Deliverable 5:

1. Grey literature. Manual searching of approximately 20 organisational repositories (CGIAR, World Bank, 3ie, GCF, FAO, IFAD, regional development banks) is pending.
2. Preliminary data extraction. Data extraction is LLM-assisted and has not yet been validated by human reviewers. The random sample of included studies will be subject to full human coding and validation prior to Deliverable 5.

7. Next Steps

The following steps are planned prior to the final systematic map (Deliverable 5):

- Grey literature search – manual search of approximately 20 organisational repositories per the protocol (Deliverable 3, §3.3);
- Random sampling of included studies – draw a reproducible random subset from the pool of included full-text records to serve as the basis for detailed data extraction and analysis.
- Human data extraction (sampled subset) – conduct structured, codebook-based data extraction on the sampled subset using two trained reviewers working iteratively in small batches; all extracted data will be fully human-coded and validated.
- Iterative codebook refinement and convergence assessment – continue data extraction in batches while tracking the emergence of new adaptation focus categories and methodological approaches; extend the sample as needed until convergence is reached (defined as minimal new codes across successive batches).
- Coverage check and targeted top-up sampling (if required) – assess the sampled subset for broad coverage across key dimensions (e.g., geography, adaptation types, methodological approaches) and conduct limited additional sampling where substantial gaps are identified.
- Protocol amendment (Deliverable 5.7) – documenting all deviations from Deliverable 3, including: random sampling, field 16 consolidation, and net-new database additions.
- Final systematic map (Deliverable 5) – updated ROSES flow diagram, final searchable extraction database, evidence gap map, and full systematic map report.

8. Conclusions

This preliminary systematic map provides an initial characterisation of the evidence base on methods used to track and measure climate adaptation processes and outcomes for smallholder producers in the agriculture sector in LMICs. The evidence base is substantial: 2,750 records have been coded in this preliminary pass, concentrated in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, with survey-based and quasi-experimental methods dominating. These findings confirm both the scope and the methodological fragmentation of the field identified in Deliverable 3. The full systematic map (Deliverable 5) will integrate all databases, complete full-text screening and human-validated data extraction, and provide a definitive, citable evidence base for the subsequent systematic review.

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10. References

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